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Complexes of some Bivalent Metal Ions with
4-Salicylaldimino-3-mercapto-5-phenyl-
1,2,4-triazole

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WE report the preparation and characterisation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes with 4-salicylaldimino-3-mercapto-5-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole (SMPTH_2)^{1,2}.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes : An aqueous ethanolic solution of metal(II) halide (0.005 mol in 50 ml) and an ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mol in 100 ml) were mixed. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 7–8 by adding concentrated ammonia and refluxed for 0.5 h. The Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes separated immediately but the Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II}

complexes separated on adding an equal volume of water. The complexes were filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried (90–100°).

The complexes were characterised on the basis of their elemental analyses, room temperature (304°), magnetic moment (μ_{eff}), uv and ir spectral data.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses (Table 1) correspond to 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry for all the complexes.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % :		Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
	Found/(Calcd.)	M N		
$[\text{Ni}(\text{SMPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	14.98 (15.10)	14.89 (14.40)	755 (777)	2.67
$[\text{Co}(\text{SMPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	15.32 (15.15)	14.28 (14.89)	758 (778)	4.92
$\text{Cu}(\text{SMPT})$	17.94 (17.76)	15.73 (15.65)	682 (715)	1.62
$\text{Zn}(\text{SMPT})$	18.31 (18.18)	15.31 (15.57)	698 (719)	Dia.
$\text{Cd}(\text{SMPT})$	27.71 (27.64)	13.81 (13.77)	793 (813)	Dia.

The complexes were found to be slightly soluble in DMF, dioxane, ethanol and acetone but insoluble in benzene and chloroform. Insolubility of the complexes restricted accurate determination of their molecular weight ; though approximate values (Rast method in camphor) correspond to dimeric formula of the complexes. The solutions of the complexes are almost non-conducting indicating their non-ionic nature.

The room temperature μ_{eff} values of 4.92 B.M. for $[\text{Co}(\text{SMPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and 2.67 B.M. for $[\text{Ni}(\text{SMPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ indicate spin-free octahedral nature of the metal ions. A slightly lower μ_{eff} of the Ni^{II} complex (2.98 B.M. expected for a spin-free octahedral geometry) can be attributed to the dimeric species. A subnormal μ_{eff} value of 1.62 B.M. for $\text{Cu}(\text{SMPT})$ suggests copper–copper bonding or superexchange interaction through bridging oxygen atom in the complex molecules^{3,4}.

The medium band at 19 240 cm^{-1} and a shoulder near 22 730 cm^{-1} in the reflectance spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{SMPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ were assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition and spin-orbit coupling in ${}^4T_{1g}(P)$ state respectively^{5,7} in the octahedral field. The medium broad band at 16 130 cm^{-1} and a weak band at 17 240 cm^{-1} in the reflectance spectra of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SMPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ were attributable to splitted ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ transition in a distorted octahedral field ; 23 250 cm^{-1} was due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition⁸⁻¹⁰ in the octahedral field. In solution, the complex displayed these transitions as medium and broad bands at 16 350 ($\epsilon_{\text{max}}=22$) and 23 450 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon_{\text{max}}=46$) respectively. A broad asymmetric band at 12 500–15 040 cm^{-1} and a strong band around

25 000 cm^{-1} in the reflectance spectra of Cu(SMPT) arise from a combination of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g} + {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions respectively in a tetragonal field⁶.

In 3μ region the ligand displays medium and broad bands at 3 290 and 3 090 cm^{-1} assignable to OH and CH stretches. The complexes display only one band at $3\,040 \pm 60 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, but in aquo-complexes a broad band is observed at $3\,450\text{--}3\,050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The free ligand displays a weak and broad band at $2\,758 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to SH+hydrogen bonded OH stretches. In complexes, the SH stretches disappear suggesting coordination of thiol sulphur on deprotonation. In the region $1\,620\text{--}1\,237 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, the ligand displays a number of bands at 1 620, 1 610, 1 575, 1 533, 1 495, 1 485, 1 423, 1 373, 1 295 and $1\,237 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to phenyl and triazole ring skeletal vibrations. The ir band at $1\,620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to aldimino $\nu_{C=N}$ shifted to lower frequency by 5–30 cm^{-1} indicating the involvement of C=N nitrogen in coordination. A strong band at $1\,575 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in ir spectrum of the ligand is assigned to $\nu_{C=N}$ vibrations of triazole ring. The band shifted to higher frequency in almost all the complexes. The blue-shift of $\nu_{C=N}$ band indicates the bonding of C=N nitrogen with the metal atom¹¹. The ir band at $1\,533 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to thioamide band-I¹²⁻¹⁴. As expected this band shifted to higher wave number and merge together with other C=N stretch and observed near $1\,590\text{--}1\,615 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The thioamide band-II ($1\,237 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) also shifted to higher wave number and was observed near $1\,248 \pm 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The thioamide band-III ($1\,035 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was observed as a very weak band near $1\,067 \pm 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. The shifting of thioamide band I, II and III to higher wave numbers indicates the involvement of thioamide group in coordination. The thioamide band-IV (754 cm^{-1}) also moved to lower frequencies and was observed near $705 \pm 8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to coordination of thioamide sulphur in these complexes. A broad band at $1\,373 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ of free ligand which disappeared in the complexes was assigned to δ_{OH} . A medium band at $1\,130 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ir spectra of the free ligand was assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ (phenolic) vibration. In complexes the $\nu_{C=O}$ shifted to $1\,403 \pm 18 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that double bond character of CO has increased, as usually observed in the complexes^{11,12} with bridged phenolic oxygen. A medium band near $848 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in aquo-copper(II) and -nickel(II) complexes indicated the involvement of water molecules in coordination¹⁵. The ligand displayed a number of bands in the range $690\text{--}450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which were assigned to ring deformation vibrations. In the complexes these are affected slightly due to drainage of electron density towards metal ions on coordination.

Thus from infrared spectral studies it is inferred that the ligand is bonded through deprotonated thiol sulphur, phenolic oxygen, and aldimino C=N nitrogen.

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Manganese(II), Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes with Cytosine

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CYTOSINE possesses four different potential metal binding sites as indicated by asterisk in 1. Though some reports^{1,2} are available in the literature where cytosine acts as a bidentate ligand, very few reports³ of cytosine acting as a monodentate ligand are available. The crystal structure of three metal complexes of cytosine have been reported¹ and all three are copper(II) complexes containing neutral cytosine ligand coordinating through the N(3) position of the ring and an axial intramolecular Cu...O(2) interaction. In 2:1 cytosine-CaCl₂ and in 1:1 cytosine-CaCl₂ adducts cytosine is found to act as chelating ligand coordinating through its N(3) and C(2)=O. The tetrahedral complex CoL₂(ClO₄)₂, where L=cytosine, contains

1

a monodentate coordination of cytosine through its N(3). As the N(1) position of cytosine is attached to ribose in a nucleoside or a ribose